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A Study on Awareness Regarding Pardhan Mantri Matrtiav Vandana Yojana Among Lactating Mothers in Haryana

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For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>**Vandana Kumari**Assistant Professor
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Abstract Breast feeding is natural and traditional infant feeding practice prevalent throughout the world. The mothers should adopt the exclusive breastfeeding to achieve the optimum growth and health of infants. It is a natural method to provide ideal food which necessary for the healthy development of the infants. Apart from this, breastfeeding has a unique biological and emotional impact on the health of infant and mother as well. The natural property of breastfeeding is that it protects the infant against infections and diseases. It contains the right amount and right kind of nutrients required by the child. Breastfeeding is almost universal. But the education of mother, socio- economic status, custom and beliefs also play a significant role in breastfeeding.

Keywords Pardhan Mantri Matrtiav Vandana Yojana, Awareness, Lactating Mothers.

Introduction Awareness is a concept about knowing, perceiving and being cognizant of events. Another definition describes it as a state wherein a subject is aware of some information when that information is directly available to bring to bear in the direction of a wide range of behavioral actions. The concept is often synonymous to consciousness and is also understood as being consciousness itself. The states of awareness are also associated with the states of experience so that the structure represented in awareness is mirrored in the structure of experience.

Objective of study

The present study analysis the "AWARENESS REGARDING PARDHAN MANTRI MATRITAV VANDANA YOJANA AMONG LACTATING MOTHERS IN HARYANA".

Review of Literature

WHO (1998) reported that for the promotion of breastfeeding it was considered important that pregnant women were informed well about infant feeding and were prepared for this Duty of motherhood. They should be educated completely so that they can make well informed decisions.

WHO Breastfeeding Survey (2017) recommended that "babies should be breastfeed exclusively in the first 6 months. Result of the breast feeding survey 2017 revealed that the median age of introduction of complementary food to infants was 6 months 0 week. Regarding the feeding practice at 6 months of age 27.9% of infants were fed with breast milk without using any formula milk of this about 27% of surveyed infants continued to be fed with breast milk white taking complementary food at 6 months of age Whereas 0.9% of infants had not started complementary feeding at 6 months and was fed with breastfeeding only".

Main Text

Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana

The Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) is a scheme that helps lactating mothers by providing financial support and cash incentives. This scheme helps to improve the health and nutrition of the mother and child. It also helps to address the issue of undernourishment in women.

Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY), previously known as the Indira Gandhi Matritva Sahyog Yojana, is a maternity benefit program run by the government of India. It was originally launched in 2010 and renamed in 2017. The scheme is implemented by the Ministry of Women and Child Development. It is a conditional cash transfer scheme for pregnant and lactating women of 19 years of age or above for the first live birth.

In 2013, the scheme was brought under the *National Food Security Act, 2013* to implement the provision of cash maternity benefit of ₹6,000 (US\$84) stated in the Act. Presently, the scheme is implemented on a pilot basis in 53 selected districts and proposals are under consideration to scale it up to 200 additional 'high burden districts' in 2015-16. The eligible beneficiaries would receive the incentive given under the *Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY)* for Institutional delivery and the incentive received under JSY would be accounted towards maternity benefits so that on an average a woman gets ₹6,000

The scheme, rechristened Maternity benefits programme is set to cover the entire nation. Prime Minister Narendra Modi, in his 2017 New Year's Eve speech, announced that the scheme will be scaled up to cover 650 districts of the country.^[7] The announcement assumes significance as India accounts for 17% of all maternal deaths in the world. The country's maternal mortality ratio is pegged at 113 per 100,000 live births, whereas infant mortality is estimated at 32 per 1,000 live births. Among the primary causes of high maternal and infant mortality are poor nutrition and inadequate medical care during pregnancy and childbirth.^[8]

In 2014, its name was changed as *Indira Gandhi Matritva Sahyog Yojana* and again as *Pradhan Mantri Matri Vandana Yojana*.¹¹²

The Government of India is making every effort to promote breastfeeding one of which is the Pradhan Mantri Matritva Vandana Yojana.

"Pradhan Mantri Matritva Vandana Yojana is a maternity benefit program run by the Government of India. It was introduced in 2016 and is implemented by Ministry of women and child Development. It is a conditional cash Transfer scheme for pregnant and lactating women of 19 years of age or above for first life birth.

It provides for wage-loss during child birth and child care and to provide conditions for safe delivery and good nutrition and feeding practices".

Objectives of Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana

The government-run programme aims to fulfill the following objectives:

1. To provide compensation for the wage loss in terms of cash incentives so that the woman can take adequate rest before and after delivery of the first living child. It is a partial compensation which is a part of a plan to provide a total sum of Rs. 6,000 on an average to the woman. The remaining cash incentive (of Rs. 1,000) is provided under Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) after institutional delivery.
2. To improve health seeking behaviour amongst pregnant women and lactating mothers.

Targeted Beneficiaries of PMMVY

1. All pregnant women and lactating mothers excluding the ones who are in regular employment with the Central/State Government or Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs) or those who are in receipt of similar benefits under any law.
2. All eligible pregnant women and lactating mothers who have their pregnancy on or after January 01, 2017 for the first child in the family.

The date and stage of pregnancy for a beneficiary is counted with respect to her Last Menstrual Period (LMP) date as mentioned in the Mother and Child Protection (MCP) card. Under Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY), more than 3.78

crores beneficiaries have been enrolled since inception of the Scheme in 2017-18 and till 02.02. 2024.

Sampling

As a sample, 214 women who were to deliver the babies were selected by purposive selection techniques from four civil hospitals of Haryana state. On the basis of low female literacy rate of Haryana, four district were selected. These were Mewat, Palwal, Fatehabad, and Sirsa. We have choose civil hospital in selected district. Purposive Sampling technique was employed for the selection of the respondents who are to deliver babies and admit in maternity wards in selected civil hospitals.

A sample of 214 women between 18-35 years of age among these 214 women 41 from Mewat, 62 from Palwal, 53 from Fatehabad and 58 from Sirsa were included in each district. All the information were collected with the help of interview schedule. Primary data were analyzed with Statistical software SPSS. Therefore keeping in view the significance of the Breastfeeding the present study was carried out in the selected mothers. All the information is collected with the help of interview schedule. Primary data is analyzed with statistical software SPSS.

Result and Discussion

The information collected during the study is condensed and a code sheet is developed for the response to create the variables in the SPSS – Software (Version 20) for the purpose of statistical analysis and data validation. In order to examine the reliability and validity of the data, the Chi Square test is used for hypothesis testing. After that it converted in to tabular form and pie charts. Statistical tools like mean, percentage analysis were used to draw inferences.

Table 1.1: Selection of The Respondents

District	Frequency	Percent
FATEHABAD	53	24.8
MEWAT	41	19.2
PALWAL	62	29.0
SIRSA	58	27.1
TOTAL	214	100.0

Table No. 1.1 show that on the basis of low female literacy rate of Haryana four district are selected. A sample of 214 women who are the deliver the babies and admit in the maternity ward are selected by purposive sampling technique.

Table No. 1.2 Awareness regarding PMMVY on the basis of Age

Sr. No.	Age group	Frequency		Percentage		
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Total
1.	18-23	49	13	23	6	29.0
2.	24-29	69	06	32	3	35.0
3.	30-35	41	08	19.2	3.7	22.9
4.	above 35	18	10	8.41	4.6	13.1
Total		177	37	82.6	17.3	100

Table No. 1.2 shows that respondents come between the age group of 18-23 years 49(23%) were aware and 13 (6 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Respondents come between the age group of 24-29 years 69(32%) were aware and 06 (3 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Respondents come between the age group of 30-35 years 41(19.2%) were aware and 08 (3.7 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Respondents above the age of 35, 18 (8.41%) were aware and 10(4.6 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Most of the respondents 82.6 % in all age groups were aware about PMMVY.

Table No. 1.3 : Educational status wise Awareness among respondents

Sr.No.	Level of Education	Frequency		Percentage		
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Total
1	Illiterate	32	69	14.9	32.3	47.2
2	Primary	29	20	13.6	9.3	22.9
3	Middle	21	8	10.2	3.7	14.0
4	Metric	18	8	8.4	3.7	12.1
5	Senior Secondary	5	2	2.4	0.9	3.3
6	Graduate	01	01	0.3	0.3	0.6
7	Postgraduate	00	00	00	00	00
Total	214	106	108	49.5	50.5	100

Table No. 1.3 shows that on the basis of education level most of the respondents 108(50.5%) out of 214 were did not know about PMMVY. Majority of the respondents who were illiterate 69(32.3%) were not aware PMMVY.

Table No. 1.4 : Working status wise Awareness among respondents

Working Status	Frequency		Percentage		
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Total
House Wife	92	65	42.9	29.5	73.4
Labour	19	30	8.8	14.1	22.9
Private Sector	06	02	2.8	0.9	3.7
Total	117	97	55.5	44.5	100.0

Table no. 1.4 demonstrates that on the basis of working status, out of the total respondents 117 (55.5%) aware and 97(44.5%) were did not aware about PMMVY.

Table No. 1.5 : Religion wise Awareness among respondents

Religion	Frequency		Percent		
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Total
Hindu	93	23	43.5	10.7	54.2
Muslim	26	35	12.2	16.3	28.5
Sikh	22	15	10.2	7.1	17.3
Total	141	73	65.9	34.1	100

The study reveals that 93(43.5) Hindu,26(12.2) Muslims,22(10.2) Sikh respondents were aware about PMMVY. Majority of 35(16.3) Muslim respondents were not aware about PMMVY.

Table No. 1.6 : Caste wise Awareness among respondents

Caste	Frequency		Percent		Total
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Backward class	44	31	20.5	14.6	35.1
General caste	47	20	21.9	9.5	31.3
Schedule caste	39	33	18.1	15.4	33.6
Total	130	84	60.5	39.5	100

The caste wise analysis of data reveals that most of the mothers 130(60.5 %) were aware about PMMVY. 84(39.5 %) respondents did not aware about PMMVY.

Table No. 1.7 : Area wise Awareness among respondents

Area	Frequency		Percent		Total
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Rural	83	53	38.9	24.7	63.6
Urban	57	21	25.6	9.8	36.4
Total	140	74	65.5	34.5	100

The study reveal that 83 (38.9%respondents from rural areas and 57 (34.5%) respondents from urban area were aware about PMMVY. 53 (24.7%respondents from rural areas and 21 (9.8%) respondents from urban area did not aware about PMMVY.

Findings

On the basis of low female literacy rate of Haryana four district were selected. A sample of 214 women who are the deliver the babies and admit in the maternity ward are selected by purposive sampling technique. Respondents come between the age group of 18-23 years 49(23%) were aware and 13 (6 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Respondents come between the age group of 24-29 years 69(32%) were aware and 06 (3 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Respondents come between the age group of 30-35years 41(19.2%) were aware and 08 (3.7 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Respondents above the age of 35 ,18 (8.41%) were aware and 10(4.6 %) respondents were not aware about PMMVY. Most of the respondents 82.6 % in all age groups were aware about PMMVY. On the basis of education level most of the respondents 108(50.5%) out of 214 were did not know about PMMVY. Majority of the respondents who were illiterate 69(32.3%) were not aware PMMVY. On the basis of working status out of the total respondents 117 (55.5%) aware and 97(44.5%) were did not aware about PMMVY. The study reveals that 93(43.5) Hindu, 26(12.2) Muslims,22(10.2) Sikh respondents were aware about PMMVY. Majority of 35(16.3) Muslim respondents were not aware about PMMVY. The caste wise analysis of data reveals that most of the mothers 130(60.5 %) were aware about PMMVY and 84(39.5 %) respondents did not aware about PMMVY. The study reveal that 83 (38.9%respondents from rural areas and 57 (34.5%) respondents from urban area were aware about PMMVY. 53 (24.7%respondents from rural areas and 21 (9.8%) respondents from urban area did not aware about PMMVY.

Conclusion Majority of the lactating mothers get information, knowledge and awareness about breastfeeding from doctors, Anganwadi works and through mass media. There is still need for programmes, which support and encourage breastfeeding at a primary level, focusing more on younger women, less well educated and those from lower socioeconomic class. The support that mothers receive from different sources such as the spouse, doctors, Aanganbadi workers, and female family members proved to be most important to breastfeeding mothers, Breastfeeding support can be increased by providing accurate information to mothers, families, the public and medical providers to increase awareness.

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